

Hepatoprotective and Anti-Inflammatory Effect of Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) And Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) in Rats Fed Breast Carcinogen

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Abstract

Cancer has been a menace to public health. Among all cancers, breast cancer is the most common in women. This research investigated the preventive effect of tomato and carrot supplementation in wistar rat administered breast carcinogen, Dimethylbenz-[a]-anthracene (DMBA). Tomato and carrot were dried under shade and pulverized. Forty-eight female rats were randomly distributed into 8 groups. Groups 1 and 2 comprised of unexposed rats fed standard diet and DMBA-administered group fed standard diet respectively. Groups 3-5 were DMBA-administered groups fed diets containing 20% tomato, 20% carrot, and 20% of an equally mixed tomato and carrot respectively. For groups 6-8, unexposed rats fed diets containing 20% tomato, carrot, and 20% of an equally mixed tomato and carrot respectively. Feeding was for a period of 10 weeks. Phytochemical characterization of the powdered plants was analyzed. Liver function parameters and inflammatory markers were assayed. Histopathology of the kidney and liver was performed. Tomato powder had higher concentrations of carotenoids (23.99 mg/100g) and phenolics (0.51 mg/100g) but lower levels of flavonoids and alkaloids than carrot powder. There were significant decreases ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of ALT, (AST) and (ALP) but an increase in the concentrations of TP in the (DMBA)-administered groups fed supplemented diets. All the groups had significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower concentrations of C-reactive protein and tumor necrosis factor- α in comparison with the DMBA-administered group fed the standard diet. The DMBA-administered groups fed supplemented diets had improved cellular architecture in comparison with the DMBA-administered group fed standard diet. Supplementation of diets with either carrot or tomato reduces the risk of breast cancer in rats exposed to DMBA by ameliorating liver dysfunction, improving anti-inflammatory defense systems and by protecting cellular integrity. coordinated awareness about the importance of including tomato and carrot in the diet as means of preventing cancer and related diseases is encouraged.

Keywords: Breastcancer, carrot, Dimethylbenz-[a]-anthracene, inflammatory, liver, tomato

1.0 Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) and cancer are the primary cause of death worldwide with CVD superseding cancer [1]. However, statistics and trends show that over the course of this century, cancer may overtake CVD as the primary cause of premature death in the majority of nations [1]. Cancer cells can occur in liquid form as in leukemia, however, mostly occur in a solid form that appears in various tissues in many parts of the body [2]. Cancer metastasizes as it develops which invades the neighboring tissues, passing into the bloodstream, disseminating and producing colonies to far-reaching parts of the body [3, 2].

The world's first recorded case of breast cancer arises from ancient Egypt in 1500 BC and there was no cure for the cancer except palliative treatment [4]. This type of cancer denotes to an uninhibited growth and proliferation of cells initiating from breast tissue. It is typically from the lobules or the inside lining of milk ducts which provide the ducts with milk, due to mutations in the genes that maintain the health and control the proliferation of cells [5]. There are various causes or risk factors of breast cancer, and consist of age, former history of breast cancer, family history, genomic origins, hormonal causes, environmental causes, life style and dietary causes [6].

There is continuous increase in the likelihood of developing cancer due to exposure to carcinogenic chemical compounds. Aromatic hydrocarbons that are polycyclic (PAHs) are among the environmental pollutants in which exposure to them is accountable for the development of oxidative stress-related illnesses [7]. One example of a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) is 7, 12-dimethylbenz-[a]-anthracene (DMBA), which when metabolized, releases harmful reactive oxygen species that ultimately cause cancer [7]. This substance causes cancer in experimental animals, and human exposure to it through food, air, and water is increasing, making it a possible carcinogen for people. According to Selamoglu [8], breast tissue would be more susceptible to PAHs because they are stored in human fat.

Worldwide breast cancer is approximately 100 times more prevalent in women than in men, making for 10.4% of all female cancer cases [9]. Recent reports indicate higher death rate in underdeveloped nations as opposed to developed ones (15.0 vs. 12.8 per 100,000) [10]. The highest death rate is found in Nigeria, the most populated country in Africa [11]. There are drugs and other treatment models for the management of breast cancer but are generally expensive and have several adverse consequences like anemia, appetite loss, bleeding, bruising, constipation, and diarrhea, a condition that makes the fight against the cancer intractable. Inflammation has an important role in all the stages of cancer from initiation to progression and even the survival of the patient. The process of inflammation releases a number of markers in the blood that can be measured in a cost-effective way in day-to-day oncological practice [12]. Since oxidative stress and inflammation play causative roles in breast cancer, one important preventive step is modification of dietary habits that involves the intake of anti-inflammatory phytochemicals [7].

Tomato contains lycoperside, a saponin that is demonstrated to have anti-inflammatory effects [13]. and lycopene found in tomato was reported to inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 which stimulates the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-10 [14]

Lycopersicon esculentum commonly termed tomatoes are extensively eaten as processed tomato products and as a vegetable that belongs to *Solanaceae* family [15]. Chlorogenic acid, eugenol, quercetin, rutin, kaempferol, naringenin, alpha and beta carotenes, phytotene, neurosporene, and lycopene are among the fruit's many anti-oxidative

and anti-carcinogenic substances [16]. *Daucus carota* L. a member of the Apiaceae family, popularly called as carrot, a root vegetable that is enjoyed all around the world and contains fibers, minerals, and other phytochemicals [17].

Therefore, due to the increasing demand in finding out the potentials of foods with anti-inflammatory effects in decreasing the carcinogenesis in various organs, this research evaluated the role of whole *Lycopersicon esculentum* and *Daucus carota* L. powder-supplemented diets in the preventing the cancer of the breast for their cost-effectiveness, easy availability and no or low side effects.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Chemicals and feed ingredients

All chemicals were of analytical grade and obtained from trusted suppliers. Corn starch was prepared by soaking corn for 48 hours, followed by grinding and sieving (0.02 mm-mesh) and turned into powder by allowing dry at room temperature. Soya bean meal (SBM), pre-mix, salt mix, cellulose, palm oil, methionine, bone meal was procured from Central Market, Katsina.

2.2 Experimental animals

Forty-eight (48) female Wistar rats weighing averagely 120 g were purchased from animal house of Biological Science Department, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. They were kept under controlled light conditions (12-h light/dark cycle at 25°C). Water and diets were given *ad libitum*.

2.3 Identification of Samples

Tomatoes and carrots were collected from gardens in Ajiwa, Batagarawa LGA Government of Katsina and taken to Department of Plant Biology Herbarium at Federal University Dutsin-Ma for identification. The following batch numbers were given; *Solanum lycopersicum* (Tomato): V/N FUDMA/PSB/00165 and *Dacus carota* (Carrot): V/N FUDMAB/PSB/00199. The samples were separately washed with clean water, sliced and dried at room temperature under shade. The two samples were separately pulverised to pass through 0.02 mm-mesh sieve and stored in polythene bags at 25°C till required. The sieved tomato and carrot powder were mixed thoroughly in equal ratio to obtain a mixture of the fruit and vegetable.

2.4 Experimental Design

After one week of acclimatization period, the forty-eight (48) female rats weighing about 120 g were divided to have nearly the same average weight into eight groups of six (6) rats per group.

Group 1: Normal control was fed with standard rat chow.

Group 2: Positive control received a single dose of 20 mg/kg b.w of Dimethylbenz-[a]-anthracene (DMBA) (orally) in olive oil + standard rat chow

Group 3: The group received a single dose of 20mg/kg b.w of DMBA (orally) in olive oil and maintained on a 20% tomato-supplemented diet.

Group 4: The group received a single dose of 20mg/kg b.w of DMBA (orally) in olive oil and maintained on a 20% carrot-supplemented diet.

Group 5: The group received a single dose of 20mg/kg b.w of DMBA (orally) in olive oil and maintained on a 20% mixed tomato and carrot-supplemented diet.

Group 6: The group received distilled water (orally) in a single dose and maintained on a 20% tomato-supplemented diet.

Group 7: The group received distilled water (orally) in a single dose and maintained on a 20% carrot-supplemented diet.

Group 8: The group received distilled water (orally) in a single dose and maintained on 20% mixed tomato and carrot-supplemented diet.

The rats were maintained on their respective diets and water *ad libitum* for a period of 10 weeks.

2.5 Sacrifice and Sample Collection

At the end of the 10 weeks, the rats were weighed, anesthetized with chloroform and sacrificed by cutting the jugular vein. Blood samples were collected into EDTA-treated sample bottles.

2.6 Phytochemical Analysis

2.6.1 Alkaloid Determination

This procedure followed Harbone [18]. The powdered sample (5g) was weighed (W_1) into a flask and 50ml of 10% acetic acid in ethanol was added. It was allowed to stand for 4hrs at 28°C and was filtered. The filtrate was heated in a hot plate to one-quarter of its original volume by evaporation. The remaining concentrate was treated with drop wise addition of 5ml of ammonium hydroxide solution until all the alkaloid was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered through the pre-weighed (W_2) filter paper. The filter paper with the filtrate was dried in the oven at 30°C. It was allowed to cool and the dried filter paper was weighed as (W_3).

Alkaloid content was calculated

$$\% \text{ Alkaloid} = \frac{(W_3 - W_2) \times 100}{\text{Wt of sample } (W_1)}$$

Where: W_3 = Weight of filter paper + filtrate; W_2 = Weight of filter paper; W_1 = Weight of sample

2.6.2 Flavonoid Determination

This procedure followed Harbone [18]. Exactly 2g of the sample was weighed (W_1) into a conical flask and 50ml of 2M HCl was added to it. The mixture was boiled for 30 minutes, cooled and filtered. Five milligrams (5ml) of filtrate were pipetted into another flask and 5ml of ethyl acetate paper was then added. A filter paper was weighed (W_2) and the precipitate was filtered through the pre-weighed paper. The filter paper with the filtrate was dried in the oven at 30°C, allowed to cool and the dried filter paper was weighed as (W_3). Flavonoid content was calculated using;

$$\% \text{ Flavonoid} = \frac{(W_3 - W_2) \times 100}{W_1}$$

Where W_1 = weigh of sample taken, W_2 = weight of pre-weighed filter paper before oven-drying,

2.6.3 Carotenoids Determination

This procedure followed Umiel [19]. Exactly 20ml of 50% methanol was added in to 0.2g of the sample. The mixture was covered with paraffin and placed in a water bath at 80°C for 1hr. It was allowed to cool and the mixture was filtered using whatman filter paper in to 100ml volumetric flask and distilled water was added to make up 100ml mark. 1ml of the filtrate was pipetted into 50ml volumetric flask. 20ml of distilled H₂O was added in to the sample and standard. 2.5ml Folin-Dennis reagent was added in to the sample and the

standard and 10ml of 17% sodium carbonate solution was added to the sample and the standard. They were mixed properly and distilled H₂O was added to make up to 50ml mark. It was allowed to stand for 20minutes for a bluish-green color to develop. Absorbance was read at 760nm.

$$\% \text{ Carotenoids} = \frac{\text{Abs} \times \text{Average Gradient} \times \text{D.F}}{\text{Wt of sample} \times 1000}$$

Where D.F. = Dilution factor

2.6.4 Determination of Total Phenolics

This procedure followed Singleton [20]. Exactly 0.5ml of the sample was pipetted into a 50ml volumetric flask, 35ml of distilled water was added to sample and standard. Exactly 2.5ml folinciocalteau (FC) reagent was added. The mixture was swirled and incubated for 1 to 8mins at room temperature after which 7.5ml sodium carbonate solution was added. Distilled water was added to makeup to the 50ml line and the mixture was incubated 2hrs at room temperature. The absorbance was read at 765 nm in a spectrophotometer.

2.7 Feed Formulation

Standard rodent diet was prepared by approximately mixing corn starch, soybean meal (SBM), methionine, mineral mix, vitamin mix, cellulose, palm oil, salt and bone meal as in Table 3.1 [21].

Table 3.1: Components of the standard rat chow

Feed component	Control diet (g/kg)
Corn starch	554.5
SBM	320
Cellulose	45
Bone Meal	12.5
Palm oil	60
Salt mix	3
Pre-mix	2.5
Methionine	2.5
Total	1000

2.8 Diet Supplementations

The supplemented diet was formulated by mixing thoroughly 80 g of standard rat chow with 20 g of each of tomato, carrot powder and a mixture of the two to get diets based on 20% supplementation of each [22].

2.9 Liver Function Test

2.9.1 Determination of Aspartate Amino Transferase (AST)

The activities of AST were determined with Randox Kit based on the method described by Reitman and Frankel [23] and subsequently modified by Schmidt and Schmidt [24]. 0.1 ml of the sample was pipetted into a tube having 0.5 ml of reagent 1 which is of phosphate buffer L-aspartate and α -oxoglutarate. It was incubated in water bath at 28 °C for 10 minutes. The sample was replaced with 0.5 ml of distilled water to constitute the blank. This was followed incubation at 37°C for 30 minutes and then addition of 0.5 ml of reagent 2; 2,4- dinitrophenylhydrazine to both the sample and blank tubes. The reaction was stopped by addition of 5 ml of 0.4N NaOH after re-incubation at 25°C for 20 minutes. The absorbance of the sample was read against the reagent blank at 546 nm after 5minutes. The activity of the transaminase was calculated from the absorbance/UI calibration curve.

2.9.2 Determination of Alanine Amino Transferase

The alanine-aminotransferase activity was determined using ALT Randox Kit based on the method of Reitman and Frankel [23] modified by Schmidt and Schmidt [24]. The sample (0.1 ml) was pipette into a tube containing 0.5 ml of the reagent 1 (Phosphate buffer, L-alanine and α -oxoglutarate). The mixture was incubated for 10 minutes at 28 °C. The blank was constituted by replacing the sample with 0.5 ml of distilled water. The reaction constituents in each tube were thoroughly mixed and incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. This was followed by the addition of 0.5 ml of reagent 2 (2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine) to both the sample and blank tubes. The reaction constituents in each tube were thoroughly mixed and re-incubated at 25°C for 20 minutes after which 5 ml of 0.4N NaOH was added to stop the reaction. The resulting solution was mixed well and the absorbance of the sample was read against the reagent blank at 546 nm after 5 minutes. The activity of alanine-aminotransferase in the serum and tissue homogenate was obtained from the absorbance/UI Calibration Curve

2.9.3 Determination of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP)

ALP Activity was determined as recommended by the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Klinische Chemie

[25]. A ml of the reagent constituted of p-nitrophenylphosphate, diethanolamine buffer and $MgCl_2$ was added to 0.02 ml of the sample and mixed thoroughly. The initial absorbance was read at 405 nm and then again after 1, 2 and 3 minutes.

$$ALP (U/l) = 2760 \times \Delta A405$$

where ΔA is Change in absorbance and 2760 is the Standard concentration.

2.9.4 Determination of Total and Conjugated Bilirubin

Determination of Total Bilirubin

The kit for determination of serum concentration of total bilirubin was based on the method of Jendrassik and Grof [26]. A 0.2 ml of Reagents R1 (sulphanilic acid and hydrochloric acid), 0.05 ml of R2 (sodium nitrite), 1 ml of R3 (caffeine and sodium benzoate) and 0.20 ml of sample were added in a tube and incubated at 25 °C for 10 minutes. Then 1 ml of R4 (tartrate and sodium hydroxide) was added and the whole constituents was mixed and incubated at 25 °C for another 10 minutes. The absorbance of the sample was read against the sample blank at 579 nm.

$$Total\ bilirubin\ (\mu\text{mol/l}) = 184 \times A_{\text{sample}}$$

where 185 = standard concentration and A_{sample} is the absorbance of sample.

Determination of direct (conjugate) bilirubin

The kit for determination of serum concentration of direct (conjugate) bilirubin was also based on the method of Jendrassik and Grof [26] (1938). A 0.20 ml of Reagents R1 (sulphanilic acid and hydrochloric acid), 0.05 ml of reagent R2 (sodium nitrite), 2 ml of 0.9% NaCl and 0.20 ml of sample were added and incubated for 10 minutes at 25°C. The absorbance of sample was read against the sample blank at 546 nm.

$$Direct\ bilirubin\ \left(\mu\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{l}}\right) = 246 \times A_{\text{sample}}$$

$$Direct\ bilirubin\ (\mu\text{mol/l}) = 246 \times A_{\text{sample}}$$

Where 246 is the standard concentration and A_{sample} is the absorbance of sample.

2.9.5 Total Protein

The kit for determination of serum of total protein was based on the biuret reaction method by Tietz,

[27]. A 1.00 ml of biuret reagent was pipetted into three test tubes labeled reagent blank, standard and sample. 0.020 ml distilled water, 0.02ml standard and 0.02 ml test sample were added into the test tubes respectively. The contents were mixed and incubated at 25 °C. The absorbance of the sample (A_{sample}) and that of standard (A_{standard}) were measured against the reagent blank.

$$Total\ protein = \left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{standard}}}\right) \times \text{Standard concentration}$$

2.9.6 Albumin

The serum albumin was determined by the method described by Doumas et al. [28]. To constitute the reaction mixture, 3 ml of BCG reagent 1 (succinate buffer, bromocresol green, Brij 35 and preservative) and 0.01 ml of the sample were added in a test tube. The standard was constituted by replacing the sample with 0.01 ml of standard (Cal). The blank was also constituted by replacing the sample with 0.01 ml of distilled water. The reaction constituents in each tube were thoroughly mixed and incubated at 25°C for 5 minutes. The absorbance of sample and standard was read against the reagent blank at 630 nm.

$$Albumin\ conc.\ \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}}\right) = \frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{standard}}} \times \text{Conc. of stand.}$$

2.9.7 Determination of serum globulin

The serum globulin was calculated from the following expression;

$$Globulin = Total\ protein - Albumin [29].$$

2.10.0 Estimation of Inflammatory Markers

2.10.1 Determination of C-Reactive Protein

This procedure followed Singer [30]. Control, 20 μl of each calibrator and diluted specimen sample were pipette into correspondingly labeled wells in duplicate. 200 μl of assay buffer was pipette into each well and incubate on a plate shaker for 30 minutes at room temperature. The wells were washed three times with 300 μl of diluted buffer per well and the plate was taped firmly against absorbent paper to ensure it is well dried. 100 μl of the conjugate was pipette on a plate shaker for 15 mins at room temperature. The wells were washed again as done previously. 100 μl of TMP substrate was pipette into each well at time intervals. It was then incubated on a plate shaker for 10-15mins at room temperature. 50 μl of stopping solution was pipette into each well at the same time interval as

done previously. The plate on a micro plate reader was read at 450nm within 20mins after addition of stop solution.

2.10.2 Determination of Interleukin-6 (IL-6)

This procedure followed Helle et al. [31]. Blank, 100 μ l of diluted standards and diluted samples were pipette, preferably in duplicate, into appropriate wells. The plate was incubated at room temperature (25°C) for 1 hour, shaken at 300rpm on orbital microplate shaker. The wells were washed 3 times with wash solution (0.35ml per well) after final wash, the plate strongly inverted and taped against paper towel. 100 μ l of biotin labelled antibody solution was pipetted into each well. The plate was incubated at room temperature (at 25°C) for 30 mins, shaken at 300 rpm on an orbital microplate shaker. The wells were washed 3 times with wash solution into each well. Exposure of the microtiter plate to direct sunlight was avoided and the plate was covered with aluminium foil. The plate was incubated for 10minutes at room temperature. Color development was stopped by adding 100 μ l of stop solution. The absorbance of each well was determined using a micro plate reader at 450 nm, preferably with the reference wavelength set to 630 nm, readings at 630 nm were subtracted from readings at 450nm. The absorbance was read within 5min following the addition of the stop solution.

2.10.3 Determination of TNF- α

This procedure followed Yener et al. [32]. All reagents and samples were kept at room temperature. In each well 50 μ l of assay diluent (1F) was added, Assay diluent 1F was precipitated. Samples were well mixed before and during use. 200 μ l of standard and sample were added per well and were covered with the adhesive strip provided were incubated for two hours at room temperature. A plate layout was provided to record standards and samples assayed. Each well was aspirated and washed; the process was repeated twice for a total of three washes. Each well was washed by filling with it wash buffer (400 μ l) using a squirt bottle, multi-channel pipette, manifold dispenser or auto washer. Complete removal of liquid at each step is essential to good performance. After the last wash, the wash buffer was removed by aspirating or decanting. The plate was inverted and blotted against clean paper toweling. 200 μ l of TNF- α conjugate was added to each well and was covered with a new adhesive strip for serum sample. It was

incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. Aspiration/wash was repeated as done before. 200 μ l of substrate solution was added to each well and incubated for 20 minutes at room temperature. 50 μ l of stop solution was added to each well. Optical density of each well was determined within 30 minutes using a microplate reader set at 450 nm. If wavelength correction is available set to 450 nm or 570nm. If wavelength correction is not available, subtract readings at 540nm or 570nm from the reading at 540nm. This subtraction will correct for optical imperfections in the plate. Readings made directly at 450nm without correction higher and less accurate.

2.11 Histological Analysis

A portion of each of the harvested organs (liver and kidney) from a rat per group was cut and stored in 10% formaldehyde for histopathological studies, dehydrated through graded alcohol series embedded in paraffin, cut into 5 mm sections and stained with hematoxylin-eosin (H and E) and periodic acid Schiff base (PAS) method. The slides were examined by light microscope on 400 x magnification for microscopic alterations of pathological significance [33].

2.12 Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from the experiment were analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) software for windows version 21 (SPSS Inc., Chicago Illinois, USA) the results were reported as Mean \pm SEM of the values and Duncan comparison was used to compare the mean values. P<0.05 was considered significant.

3.0 Results

3.1 Phytochemical Composition of Tomato and Carrot

Table 4.1 shows phytochemical characterization of tomato and carrot. Alkaloids, carotenoids flavonoids and phenolic compounds, were present in the tomato and carrot at various concentrations. Tomato powder had higher concentrations of carotenoids (23.99 mg/100g) and phynolics (40.45 mg/100g) than carrot which had 0.51 mg/100g and 0.88 mg/100g of carotenoids and phynolics respectively. However, flavonoids and alkaloids were higher in concentrations in carrot powder than the levels found in tomato powder.

Table 3.1 Phytochemical Composition of tomato and carrot

Phytochemical	Tomato	Carrot
Carotenoids (mg/100g)	23.99±0.31	0.51±0.00
Phenolics (mg/100g)	40.45±0.02	0.88±0.00
Flavanoids (mg/100g)	9.03±0.02	21.58±0.66
Alkaloids (mg/100g)	2.69±0.13	14.18±0.31

The result represents the average of three determinants with the standard error of the mean indicated by Mean±SEM.

3.2 Parameters of Liver Function in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot-Supplemented Diet

Table 3.2 indicates significant increase ($p<0.05$) in the activities of ALT, AST, ALP and the concentrations of TB but significant decrease ($p<0.05$) in the concentration of TP in breast

carcinogen-administered group fed standard diet when compared with the normal group. However, feeding on tomato and carrot supplemented diet resulted in the significant decrease ($p<0.05$) in the activities of ALT, AST and ALP but an increase in the concentration of TP and ALB in comparison with the breast carcinogen-administered group fed standard diet.

Table 3.2: Parameters of Liver Function in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

Gp	ALT (μ l)	AST (μ l)	ALP (μ l)	TP (g/dl)	ALB (g/dl)	DB (mmol/l)	TB (mmol/l)
1	19.5±5.33 ^{abc}	18.3±1.44 ^a	22.6±3.07 ^a	8.25±0.42 ^{bc}	1.60±0.71 ^{ab}	4.05±0.39 ^a	15.75±0.64 ^a
2	27.3±4.21 ^c	49.0±13.5 ^c	33.4±3.22 ^b	4.73±0.32 ^a	1.00±0.17 ^a	5.92±0.30 ^a	17.05±0.96 ^b
3	13.0±1.63 ^a	7.25±2.39 ^a	27.2±2.25 ^a	6.13±0.35 ^b	1.55±0.17 ^b	5.08±0.49 ^a	14.75±0.95 ^a
4	19.0±2.48 ^{ab}	24.8±7.48 ^{ab}	25.3±2.83 ^a	7.88±0.59 ^{bc}	1.63±0.41 ^b	5.70±1.21 ^a	16.33±0.51 ^b
5	15.5±1.32 ^{ab}	12.8±1.03 ^a	28.5±5.39 ^a	5.33±0.47 ^b	1.93±0.43 ^{bc}	4.50±0.53 ^a	14.33±1.22 ^a
6	25.5±3.38 ^{bc}	27.2±2.14 ^b	19.6±0.70 ^a	8.28±1.52 ^{bc}	2.83±0.58 ^c	4.78±0.67 ^a	14.08±1.12 ^a
7	16.5±2.63 ^{ab}	18.5±8.15 ^a	22.8±2.69 ^a	6.00±0.68 ^b	1.55±0.23 ^b	4.25±0.36 ^a	14.45±1.13 ^a
8	12.8±2.02 ^a	17.8±1.75 ^a	24.3±3.13 ^a	9.78±0.53 ^c	2.10±0.71 ^{bc}	4.20±0.21 ^a	12.53±1.01 ^a

The result represents the average of four determinants, with the standard error of the mean indicated by Mean±SEM. Values with identical superscripts do not exhibit significant differences ($P>0.05$), while values with different super script exhibit significant differences. Key: ALT: Alanine amino transferase, AST: Aspartate amino transferase, ALP: Alkaline phosphatase, TP: Total protein, ALB: Albumin, DB: Direct bilirubin, TB: Total bilirubin. Group 1: normal rats Fed standard rat chow. Group 2; DMBA administered group Fed standard rat chow. Group 3: DMBA administered group Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet. Group 4: DMBA administered group Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet. Group 5: DMBA administered group fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet. Group 6: normal rats Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet. Group 7: normal rats Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet. Group 8: normal rats Fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet.

3.3 Inflammatory Markers of DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot-Supplemented Diets

The serum concentrations of the inflammatory biomarkers in DMBA-administered Wistar rats fed tomato and carrot-supplemented diets are shown in Table 4.9. There were significant increases ($p < 0.05$) in the concentrations of CRP and TNF- α in the DMBA-administered group when compared with normal control. However, feeding on tomato and carrot supplemented diet resulted in

significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in the concentrations of CRP and TNF- α in comparison with the DMBA-administered group fed standard diet. There were no significant differences in the concentration of IL-6 within the groups. Normal rats fed tomato-supplemented diet had significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower CRP, while the normal rats fed carrot-supplemented diet or mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher CRP when compared with the normal control.

Table 3.3: Inflammatory Markers of DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot-Supplemented Diets

Group	CRP (mg/ml)	IL6 (pg/ml)	TNF (pg/ml)
1	346.4 \pm 8.57 ^a	108.3 \pm 8.608 ^a	168.5 \pm 11.94 ^{bc}
2	598.4 \pm 14.8 ^c	131.8 \pm 23.88 ^a	274.3 \pm 33.40 ^d
3	457.7 \pm 6.31 ^b	94.63 \pm 8.598 ^a	104.5 \pm 4.167 ^a
4	498.2 \pm 10.34 ^b	110.2 \pm 17.26 ^a	198.9 \pm 16.52 ^c
5	494.4 \pm 10.5 ^b	134.7 \pm 21.98 ^a	108.9 \pm 6.210 ^a
6	317.8 \pm 4.35 ^d	108.9 \pm 30.24 ^a	136.3 \pm 15.11 ^{ab}
7	474.4 \pm 7.30 ^b	99.68 \pm 3.771 ^a	122.1 \pm 4.740 ^{ab}
8	422.3 \pm 6.90 ^b	87.68 \pm 5.042 ^a	102.1 \pm 5.648 ^a

The result represents the average of four determinant, with the standard error of the mean indicated by Mean \pm SEM. Values with identical superscripts do not exhibit significant differences ($P > 0.05$), while values with different super script exhibit significant differences. Key: CRP: C-Reactive protein, IL-6: Interleukin 6 and TNF: Tumor necrosis factor alpha. Group 1: normal rats Fed standard rat chow. Group 2; DMBA administered group Fed standard rat chow. Group 3: DMBA administered group Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet. Group 4: DMBA administered group Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet. Group 5: DMBA administered group fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet. Group 6: normal rats Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet. Group 7: normal rats Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet. Group 8: normal rats Fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet.

3.4 Kidney Histopathology of DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot-Supplemented Diets

Plate 3.1 indicates kidney histopathology of DMBA-administered Wistar rats fed tomato and carrot-supplemented diet. The images showed DMBA caused oxidative damage to the kidney

tissues which resulted to tumor necrosis in the breast DMBA-administered group when compared with the normal control. However, feeding with tomato and carrot supplemented diet resulted to decrease in the degree of the damage in comparison with the breast DMBA-administered group.

Group 1: normal rats Fed standard rat chow showing normal feature, Group 2: DMBA administered group fed standard rat chow showing tumor necrosis, Group 3: DMBA administered group Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet showing slight hyperplasia of inflammatory cells, Group 4: DMBA administered group Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet showing tubular adhesion with hyperplasia of inflammatory cells, Group 5: DMBA administered group fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet showing slight necrosis. Group 6: normal rats Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet showing normal feature Group 7: normal rats Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet showing normal feature and Group 8: normal rats fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet showing normal feature.

Plate 3.1: Kidney Histopathology by Wistar Rats exposed to Breast Carcinogen (DMBA) and fed with Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

Group 1: normal rats Fed standard rat chow showing normal feature, Group 2: DMBA administered group Fed standard rat chow showing slight sinusoidal congestion and hepatic necrosis, Group 3: DMBA administered group Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet showing slight vacuolation, Group 4: DMBA administered group Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet showing slight vascular congestion, Group 5: DMBA administered group fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet showing slight vacuolation and necrosis. Group 6: normal rats Fed 20% tomato-supplemented diet showing normal feature, Group 7: normal rats Fed 20% carrot-supplemented diet showing normal feature and Group 8: normal rats Fed 20% mixed tomato/carrot-supplemented diet showing normal feature.

Plate 3.2: Liver Histopathology by Wistar Rats exposed to Breast Carcinogen (DMBA) and fed with Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

3.5 Liver Histopathology of DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot-Supplemented Diets

Plate 3.2 indicates liver histopathology of Wistar rats exposed to breast carcinogen and fed with tomato and carrot supplemented diet. The images showed DMBA caused oxidative damage to the hepatic tissues which resulted to hepatic necrosis in the breast carcinogen administered group when compared with the normal control. However, feeding with tomato and carrot supplemented diet resulted to decrease in the degree of the damage in comparison with the breast carcinogen-administered group.

4.0 Discussion

4.1 Phytochemical Composition of Tomato and Carrot

Phytochemicals, though produced by plants for self-defense, have been shown to shield people from illness [34]. This finding is in agreement with several other researches that have also found the presence these phytochemicals in tomato and carrot. [35,36,37]. The presence of alkaloids, phenolic, and particularly carotenoids and flavonoids in both the dried and pulverized tomato and carrot is interesting since the compounds were reported to possess anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and plasma lipid-modifying qualities [38, 39]. It is well known that alkaloids have anesthetic, cardioprotective, and anti-inflammatory qualities [40]. Dietary polyphenols which include flavonoids and carotenoids are good in mitigating inflammation making it essential in prevention of diseases such as cancers and related diseases [41]. The physiological properties of these phenols such as their anticancer, antioxidant, and antimutagenic properties, are reported to be through scavenging of free radicals [35].

It has been shown that the anti-inflammatory activity of flavonoid is through activation of antioxidant pathways [42]. Carotenoids have been linked to better immune response and a decreased risk of degenerative diseases such as age-related macular degeneration, cancer, and heart disease [35]. The effects of polyphenols in the body is however dependent upon their quantity that are bioavailable. Several researches had similarly reported the presence of these phytochemicals in tomato and carrot [43,44,45]. The presence of tomato and carrot in the diets may therefore play a role more than the traditional functions of food as

such diets could improve health and prevent the occurrence of diseases.

4.2 Parameters of Liver Function in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

Being a very potent breast carcinogen, metabolic activation of DMBA occurs in the hepatocytes, a process that causes formation of free radicals and DMBA-DNA adducts in the hepatocytes. The free radicals consequently generated could react with macromolecules like lipid, protein and DNA, and could cause serious damage to the liver [46]. This could be seen in the significantly higher levels of the activities of the studied liver enzymes in the DMBA-administered group fed standard diet in comparison with other groups. These enzymes are released from injured hepatocytes causing their rise in the serum [47]. The results indicate that supplementation with tomato and /or carrot could protect the liver from damages in rats subjected to breast carcinogen as indicated by the lowering of serum activities of the enzymes. Tomato is rich in lipophilic compounds like lycopene [48] which according to Liu et al. [49] protects the liver in patients of breast cancer. The improved liver function could also be due to other antioxidant phytochemical constituents of the tomato such as vitamin C, beta-carotene, phenolic and flavonoids [50] all of which scavenge free radicals [36] and prevent damage to the liver. Lycopene which is a very potent quencher of singlet oxygen is absorbed from tomato into liver and some other tissues where it could stay for about a month [51]. Carotenoids of tomato are also precursors of vitamin A. This vitamin prevents hepatocellular carcinoma by rejuvenating the shape of hepatic stellate cells [52], another possible means of hepatoprotection by tomato. The result is consistent with the observed increase in feed intake and percentage weight rise in the groups fed the supplemented diets since poor feeding could affect the function and structure of the liver. The finding also agrees with Amaechi et al. [47] who reported that consumption of tomato decreases serum liver enzyme activities and play a role in regeneration of liver cell damage. Ujowundu et al. [53] had long reported that tomato extract reduces liver dysfunction caused by polyaromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH) like DMBA. Like the tomato-supplemented diet, carrot-supplemented diet mitigated against poor feed intake and loss of weight associated with exposure to the carcinogen. Further, carrot is also rich in carotenoids (particularly carotene) and provitamin A [54]. Carotene has been shown by many studies to have

a hepatoprotective effect due to their free radical scavenging ability and due to their modulating effects on genes of lipid metabolism in hepatocytes [55, 56]. It was reported that biologically active form of vitamin A (retinoic acid (RA) selectively controls NKT-cell cytokine production and as such control's hepatic inflammation [57]. In addition, carrot contains free radical-scavenging flavonoids and phenolic derivatives. These phytonutrients also decrease inflammatory insult, improve immunological response [58] and therefore could protect the liver from environmental and non-environmental insults. Extract of carrot was earlier reported by the same researchers to lower serum ALT and AST [58] which is consistent with the finding in this research. The combination of both tomato and carrot in a diet may not have hepatoprotective advantages over the use of either of the two as shown by the activities of the studied enzymes in the groups fed a combination of the two. This may not be unconnected with the similarity in the phytonutrient contents of both tomato and carrot.

Bilirubin is the product of metabolism breakdown of hemoglobin and heme-containing proteins like myoglobin and cytochromes [59]. The non-significant difference seen in the concentrations of direct bilirubin and total bilirubin suggests that cholestasis may not be part of liver function distortions linked to exposure to DMBA. Direct bilirubin is more of prognostic value in liver damage [60] than total bilirubin which has many pathophysiology that include hemolysis-causing splenomegaly [60]. The result is consistent with the no significant difference in red blood cell indices earlier presented in this work since decreased synthesis or increased hemolysis could affect the concentrations of bilirubin. From the results, it is seen that consumption of diets supplemented with tomato and/or carrot could prevent liver damage associated with metabolic handling of breast carcinogens such as DMBA.

4.3 Inflammatory Markers of Wistar in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

Inflammation is a response to many injuries, diseases, and severe trauma. The major role of inflammation is to attack infections, eliminate them from the body, and promote wound healing. However, inflammation also leads to multiple diseases, like cancer [61]. Having earlier established the ameliorating roles of tomato and/or carrot-enriched diets on carcinogen-mediated oxidative stress, the observed anti-inflammatory

activities of the diets as seen in lowered pro-inflammatory markers is not surprising. There is a feedback mechanism between the two in that oxidative stress contributes to inflammation just as inflammation is involved in oxidative stress [62]. For instance, inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) is expressed in cells during inflammation leading to continued generation of NO, also NADPH oxidase is activated with increased generation of superoxide [63]. Conversely, signaling cascades that result in inflammation are triggered by reactive oxygen species through oxidation and structural modification of biomolecules [64].

Tomato contains lycoperside, a saponin that is demonstrated to have anti-inflammatory effects [13]. Nuclear factor kappa B (NFκB) pathway which stimulates the expression of pro-inflammatory genes [49] had been reported to be inhibited by supplementation of diet with tomato powder [65], and by lycopene [66], the most bioactive ingredient in tomato. In addition to inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α and IL-6, lycopene also stimulates the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 [67]. The results agree partially with Widjaja et al. [68] who reported that intake of tomato only lowered TNF- α concentration but didn't affect the concentrations of CRP and IL-6. Quercetin, kaempferol and luteolin are among the flavonoids in carrot and are reported to counter inflammation. Kaempferol suppresses the binding of NFκB from DNA thereby reducing the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines [69], while TNF- α and IL-6 production are reduced by luteolin [70]. Quercetin inhibits the secretions of the IL-6 and regulates the production of nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-like-receptor family pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome [71]. NLRP3 inflammasome is an important component of immune defense system, but its dysregulation could cause many inflammatory disorders [72]. Consistently, it is also seen here that mixing the phytonutrients of tomato and carrot in a diet may not exert any additional anti-inflammatory benefit against breast carcinogen mediated inflammation.

Inflammation plays crucial roles in liver degeneration and disease [73]. One of the mechanisms for the improved liver function in the groups subjected to carcinogen and fed tomato and/or carrot diet as presented earlier may involve anti-inflammatory process. Further, inflammation is implicated in various chronic ailments like diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease and

breast cancer [74, 75]. Its association with breast cancer [76] has to do with causing increased mutagenesis and predisposing the cells to accumulation of mutations and DNA damage [77]. The observed anti-inflammatory activities of diets enriched with tomato and/or carrot against breast carcinogen may therefore prove healthy and helpful in preventing breast cancer.

According to Mahesh et al. [78], 0.3 milliliters of carrot juice's β -carotene decreased the amount of high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hsCRP) by 40%. It was also reported that the concentration of CRP (C-reactive protein) decreased after tomato sage consumption (500 mL) for 2 weeks [79]. Also Yang et al. [80] indicated that administration of β -carotene for 7 days amazingly decreased production in LPS-induced intestinal inflammation. A randomized cross-sectional study also found that healthy males who consumed tomato or carrot juice following two weeks of low carotenoid periods showed improvements in tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α). This study conforms to another research by Widjaja et al. [68] who observed that eating tomato has no meaningful role on serum IL6 concentration, but can reduce serum TNF level significantly.

4.4 Kidney Histopathology in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

Histological analysis of the treated rats' kidneys revealed alterations that supported our biochemical results. DMBA caused a severe distortion in the cellular integrity of the renal tissues. This carcinogen may cause rats to develop liver damage by inducing inflammation and oxidative stress. In relation to the group given the breast carcinogen, rats supplemented with tomato and carrot diet showed less change in the histoarchitecture of the renal tissues, indicating protection against DMBA-induced histological alterations [81]. This protection can be as a result of the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potentials of tomato and carrot supplemented diet as it is evident from this research, tomato and carrot supplemented diet increased total antioxidant condition, and inhibited pro-inflammatory cytokines in the rats. Thus, the results of the histopathology showed that the cellular anti-inflammatory qualities of the polyacetylenes found in carrots inhibited inflammatory processes [81].

Also taken into account the that oxidative stress has crucial effect in the pathogenesis of nephrotoxicity. According to reports, polyphenolic

substances have nephroprotective properties via supporting the antioxidant enzyme system and reducing the release of ROS and lipid peroxidation [81]. As proof of this, the antioxidant activity of tomato and carrot polyphenolic components can aid in nephroprotection. By scavenging free radicals, natural antioxidants like β -carotene, a terpenoid component of the carrot can reduce nephrotoxicity [35]. Based on the combined outcomes of biochemical and morphologic pathology, Tomato and carrot may possessed strong antioxidant and cellular anti-inflammatory properties that allowed it to arrest the DMBA-induced nephrotoxicity. This agreed with a study by Zanna et al. [82] that found *Daucus carota* (DC) had a protective role on the architecture of the chosen tissues. The extract preserved the kidney tissue's structures that were comparable to those of the control, indicating that the extract had a protective effect on the renal histology. Additionally, another study by Sodimbakuet al. [81] supports the current study, who showed that histopathological observations revealed that the administration of an ethanolic *Daucus carota* extract dose-dependently reduced the nephrotoxic effects of gentamicin to a significant degree in rats.

4.5 Liver Histopathology in DMBA-administered Wistar Rats Fed Tomato and Carrot Supplemented Diet

The liver of the carcinogen-induced cancer rats showed hepatic necrosis and vascular congestion. Raju et al. [83] explained that the vascular congestion was caused by the inflammatory response resulting from ROS. The photomicrographs showed remarkable recovery in the hepatic tissues of the given tomato and carrot-supplemented diet compared to the breast carcinogen administered group. The endogenous antioxidant defense system is crucial for shielding cells from oxidative damage caused by ROS. Increased SOD, CAT, GSH activities in groups fed tomato and carrot-supplemented diet indicated the protective role of tomato and carrot against DMBA-induced oxidative stress through improvement of antioxidant enzymes activities in accordance to the earlier researches. This agrees with research by Zanna et al. [82] who revealed that *Daucus carota* (DC) demonstrated a protective effect in the histology of the chosen tissues. This was shown in the liver as less hepatocyte damage, the sinusoids' integrity being maintained, and the quantity of inflammatory cells in the hepatic parenchyma decreasing. Additional research by Jain et al. [84] and Sodimbaku et al.

[81] is also consistent with the current findings. examined the hepatoprotective efficacy of kaempferol, which was extracted from DC, in albino rats whose livers had been damaged by acetaminophen. According to the current investigation, oral kaempferol treatment restored all histological changes and liver parameters in a dose-dependent way.

5.0 Conclusion

The anti- breast cancer activities of tomato and carrot supplements in female rats induced with DMBA was investigated. It can be deduced that supplementation of diets containing either carrot and/or tomato ameliorates liver dysfunction, increases the anti-inflammatory defense systems and also stimulates tissue repair in rats exposed to breast carcinogen.

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